

Genome editing of a recalcitrant wine grape genotype by lipofectamine-mediated delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 ribonucleoproteins to protoplasts

Giorgio Gambino^{1,†}

¹Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, National Research Council (CNR-IPSP), Strada delle Cacce, 73, 10135 Torino, Italy, ²Research Centre for Viticulture and Enology, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA-VE), Via XXVIII Aprile 26, 31015 Conegliano, Italy, and

³Open Laboratory – Department of Veterinary Sciences, University of Turin (DSV-UNITO), Largo Paolo Braccini 2, 10095 Grugliasco, Italy

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*For correspondence (e-mail irene.perrone@ipsp.cnr.it).

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work.

SUMMARY

The main bottleneck in the application of biotechnological breeding methods to woody species is due to the *in vitro* regeneration recalcitrance shown by several genotypes. On the other side, woody species, especially grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.), use most of the pesticides and other expensive inputs in agriculture, making the development of efficient approaches of genetic improvement absolutely urgent. Genome editing is an extremely promising technique particularly for wine grape genotypes, as it allows to modify the desired gene in a single step, preserving all the quality traits selected and appreciated in elite varieties. A genome editing and regeneration protocol for the production of transgene-free grapevine plants, exploiting the lipofectamine-mediated direct delivery of CRISPR–Cas9 ribonucleoproteins (RNPs) to target the phytoene desaturase gene, is reported. We focused on Nebbiolo (*V. vinifera*), an extremely *in vitro* recalcitrant wine genotype used to produce outstanding wines, such as Barolo and Barbaresco. The use of the PEG-mediated editing method available in literature and employed for highly embryogenic grapevine genotypes did not allow the proper embryo development in the recalcitrant Nebbiolo. Lipofectamines, on the contrary, did not have a negative impact on protoplast viability and plant regeneration, leading to the obtainment of fully developed edited plants after about 5 months from the transfection. Our work represents one of the first examples of lipofectamine use for delivering editing reagents in plant protoplasts. The important result achieved for the wine grape genotype breeding could be extended to other important wine grape varieties and recalcitrant woody species.

Keywords: genome editing, protoplast regeneration, grapevine, lipofectamines, recalcitrant genotypes, *Vitis vinifera* L.

INTRODUCTION

The application of conventional breeding techniques in grapevine (*Vitis* spp.) is challenging, because of the intrinsic peculiarities of this species, such as the long reproductive cycle, highly heterozygous genome, and extended evaluation period (Vezzulli et al., 2022). While traditional breeding is commonly exploited for table grape genotypes, the introduction of new wine grape varieties is extremely difficult. That is mainly due to consumer choices pushing toward traditional and well-known cultivars and to limitations related with the cultivation of hybrid genotypes in

Protected Designation of Origin areas. The development of new breeding technique protocols working on wine genotypes, such as precision editing, is urgently needed to safeguard the elite wine grape varieties used for the production of outstanding quality wines, such as Barolo, Amarone, and Champagne. The viticultural system is in fact seriously impacted by climate-change-induced abiotic stresses and by the intensification of fungal diseases (Gill & Garg, 2014; Mosedale et al., 2016). For example, the management of *Plasmopara viticola* and *Erysiphe necator*, respectively, responsible for downy and powdery mildews,

Figure 1. Precision editing of Nebbiolo grapevines.

- (a) Embryogenic calli are produced by in vitro culturing of floral explants – (b) anthers and (c) ovaries – collected from different grapevine genotypes. Embryogenesis rate in 2021, 2022, and 2023 years is reported.
- (g–i) Confocal images of protoplasts taken at 24 h from lipofectamine-mediated transfection with the Cas9-GFP RNP complex and (d–f) negative control. Size bar = 40 μm .
- (j) Nebbiolo embryogenic callus used as starting explant to (k) isolate protoplasts. Size bar = 40 μm .
- (l) Protoplasts transfected with CRISPR/Cas9 RNP complexes targeting the *PDS* gene by means of lipofectamines and embedded in drops of nutrient medium.
- (m–n) Protoplast microcolonies (size bar = 50 μm), (o–q) micro-embryogenic structures (size bar = 100 μm), and (r–s) mature embryo formation.
- (t) Plants regenerated after two months.
- (u) A regenerated *PDS*-edited plant showing an albino phenotype and a wt plant.
- (v–w) HRM results showing edited regenerants (green and blue) and wt plants (red).
- (x) Sequencing chromatograms of the four mutations that occurred in independent lines.
- (y) Targeted NGS sequencing results and analysis of the mutations occurred in the seven edited plants.
- (z) Multiple sequence alignment of the predicted *PDS* protein of wt and mutants.

is currently carried out through an intensive use of chemical fungicide in vineyard, an approach that is no longer sustainable from both an environmental and economic perspective (Pertot et al., 2017).

Gene editing is the most promising toolbox in New Breeding Techniques (NBT) for crop trait improvement aimed at obtaining resistant and resilient plants capable of facing the emerging challenges of climate change, which disclose conditions of progressively higher biotic and abiotic stresses (Gao, 2021; Giudice et al., 2021). This technique and its potential to obtain improved genotypes, identical to the mother plant except for the desired modified trait, and without the integration of foreign DNA, represents an excellent opportunity for the genetic improvement of traditional wine grape genotypes. Due to the biological characteristics of the species and the need to preserve the features of the starting genotypes, DNA-free delivery of gene-editing machinery as ribonucleoprotein complexes (RNPs) is the most appealing solution in grapevine, as overall in woody species (Yin et al., 2017). Grapevine protoplasts are ideal for direct delivery of RNPs, although the major bottleneck related to the applicability and feasibility of gene editing in grapevine relies on the in vitro regeneration. This is a necessary but difficult process that allows to regenerate edited plants and for which many grapevine genotypes are recalcitrant (Nuzzo et al., 2022). Up to now, DNA-free editing in grapevine has been developed in some easy-to-regenerate table grape varieties (Najafi et al., 2023; Scintilla et al., 2022). Nonetheless, no protocol is currently available for genotypes particularly recalcitrant to regeneration. Among the thousands of cultivars constituting the germplasm of *Vitis vinifera*, Nebbiolo is the most ancient and most prestigious wine grape variety (Robinson et al., 2012). It is renowned for its use in producing the high-quality red wines Barolo and Barbaresco, and it is extremely recalcitrant to somatic embryogenesis (Gribaudo et al., 2017). We therefore chose this cultivar to develop a successful protocol allowing the editing and regeneration of elite wine grape genotype plants, free of foreign DNA. Lipofectamine-mediated direct delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 ribonucleoproteins (RNPs) to

Nebbiolo protoplasts was performed to silence the phytoene desaturase gene (*PDS*, Vitvi09g00004), hence obtaining albino phenotypes as visual editing proof.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nebbiolo is extremely recalcitrant to embryogenic competence

Embryogenic calli were produced by in vitro culturing of floral explants collected from different grapevine genotypes. As shown in several years of cultures, in Nebbiolo no embryogenic calli were regenerated from anther cultures and embryogenesis efficiency from ovary explants was very low with respect to Brachetto, Barbera, and Chardonnay (Figure 1a–c). These results confirmed previous findings emerged from a study conducted on 38 *V. vinifera* and rootstock genotypes that placed Nebbiolo among the cultivars characterized by low or zero embryogenic competence (Gribaudo et al., 2017). Embryogenic and regeneration competences are in fact strictly genotype-dependent, and the molecular mechanisms underlying these processes are under investigation (Nuzzo et al., 2022). It is known, for instance, that grapevine cultivars with a different embryogenic competence are characterized by a different expression level of genes involved in the early phases of the somatic embryogenesis (SE) process, such as the WUSCHEL-related homeobox (*WOX*) transcription factors *VvWOX2* and *VvWOX9* (Gambino et al., 2011). Moreover, *BABY BOOM* (*BBM*) transcription factor activity has been linked to embryogenic competence in Arabidopsis and also in grapevine (Gulzar et al., 2020; Martínez et al., 2021). Interestingly, it has also been shown in different species such as spruce, cotton, soybean, and grapevine (reviewed in Nuzzo et al., 2022) that the genotype-related SE competence is under epigenetic regulation.

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) shows high cytotoxicity on Nebbiolo protoplast cultures

Protoplasts were isolated from embryogenic calli of Nebbiolo and subjected to PEG-mediated transfection of CRISPR/Cas9 RNP complexes targeting the *PDS* gene. The

Table 1 PEG cytotoxicity test on Nebbiolo protoplasts.

Starting concentration: 8×10^5	Incubation time			
	3'	10'	20'	90'
PEG4000 25% w/v	3.73×10^5	2.66×10^5	1.74×10^5	n.d.
PEG4000 40% w/v	2.71×10^5	1.89×10^5	1.16×10^5	n.d.
PEG1500 25% w/v	4.05×10^5	2.87×10^5	2.15×10^5	n.d.
PEG1500 40% w/v	2.83×10^5	2.32×10^5	1.67×10^5	n.d.
Lipofectamine CRISPRMAX Cas9 10 μ l	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	7.44×10^5
Control	7.16×10^5	8.12×10^5	7.76×10^5	7.83×10^5

Concentration of cells is indicated as viable cells per ml. Different concentrations and molecular weights of PEG compound were used. The initial viable cell count of 8×10^5 cell ml^{-1} before PEG incubation decreased substantially to 1.16×10^5 cells ml^{-1} after PEG exposure at 40% w/v of concentration and 20 min of incubation time (conditions used in literature for editing reagent transfection, Najafi et al., 2023). Incubation with lipofectamines (conditions used for editing reagent transfection in the present work) did not impact negatively on protoplast viability. PEG solution composition: PEG4000/1500 25%/40% w/v, 0.2 M mannitol, 0.1 M $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; control: protoplasts resuspended in washing buffer (see Experimental procedures for composition). n.d. = not determined.

procedure was performed following recently established protocols working on highly embryogenic grapevine genotypes (Najafi et al., 2023; Scintilla et al., 2022). PDS is a crucial enzyme in the carotenoid biosynthesis pathway, catalyzing the breakdown of colorless phytoene into ζ -carotene and then converted into lycopene (Muruganatham et al., 2009). Using a ratio of 3:1 (90 μg :30 μg) Cas9:sgRNA and 1×10^6 cells, *PDS* gene editing was successfully achieved (Figure S1), but no regenerated plants were obtained from transfected protoplasts cultured through the agarose drop method (Najafi et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 1997). Protoplast transfection efficiency and cell viability rate are directly influenced by PEG concentration and transfection time (Biswas et al., 2022; Mahmoud et al., 2022). We evaluated PEG cytotoxicity using different PEG concentrations and molecular weights, and we found a remarkable impact of this compound on cell viability (Table 1). Moreover, we noticed that PEG-treated cultures of Nebbiolo protoplasts never developed mature embryos. The first cell divisions were observed after 10 days of culture, micro-embryogenic structures appeared after approximately 50 days, and, although cultures rarely progressed, they never produced fully developed embryos (Figure 2). PEG can affect somatic embryogenesis by altering the expression of genes regulating the embryo formation and their ability to tolerate osmotic stress in a genotype- and dose-dependent manner (Stasolla et al., 2003). In addition, the different competencies to cope with in vitro culture-induced stress conditions are at the basis of the genotype-related recalcitrance to somatic embryogenesis of different grapevine cultivars. Dal Santo et al. (2022) showed that unlike Sangiovese – a cv that readily undergoes SE – calli of the recalcitrant cultivar Cabernet Sauvignon upregulated genes related to biotic stress, stimulus responses, and secondary metabolism, hence redirecting metabolic resources toward the accumulation

Figure 2. The transfection method affects the embryo development. Embryo masses generated from 1×10^6 transfected protoplasts embedded in drops of culture medium. Lipofection (a) had a lower impact on protoplast viability with respect to PEG transfection (b). Lipofectamine-treated cultures led to embryos showing a proper development of the body plan (c and e), PEG treatment conversely stopped the embryo development at the globular stage (d and f). Size bar = 1 mm.

of defense proteins rather than toward the formation of embryogenic tissues. Similar responses were observed in coffee and spruce cultivars with low embryogenic competence (Nic-Can et al., 2015; Rutledge et al., 2013). We therefore hypothesized that PEG residues in the culture medium could have interfered with the proper embryo

development in the recalcitrant cultivar. This prompted us to test an alternative delivery method.

Lipofectamine-mediated delivery of editing reagents allows the regeneration of edited plants of the recalcitrant-to-regeneration Nebbiolo cultivar

Lipofectamine-mediated delivery of editing reagents is a consolidated technique in mammalian cells, but it is still an emerging transfection method in plants (Zhang et al., 2021). Up to now lipofection was adopted (i) in lettuce, leading to regeneration of edited plants only with the concomitant use of PEG (Park et al., 2019); (ii) in tobacco, where editing was successfully achieved in protoplasts, but no plant regeneration was obtained (Liu et al., 2020); (iii) and in citrus, where edited plants with permanent integration of T-DNA into the genome were obtained through DNA plasmid transfection (Mahmoud et al., 2022). We exploited a method exclusively based on lipofectamines to deliver CRISPR/Cas9 RNP complexes into the cells, and we achieved the regeneration of edited plants devoid of foreign DNA traces. Particularly, we tested a lipid nanoparticle transfection reagent optimized for the delivery of Cas9 protein and never used for plant cells. In citrus, it has been shown that, although using lipofectamine combined with PEG increased transfection efficiency, low levels of cell viability were recorded (Mahmoud et al., 2022). In our experiment, lipofectamines alone did not have a negative effect on protoplasts: cell viability levels were higher than PEG and similar to controls (Table 1). The ability to deliver RNPs in grapevine protoplasts by means of lipofection, without concomitant use of PEG, was explored by transfecting Nebbiolo protoplasts with a GFP-tagged Cas9 protein/sgRNA *PDS* complex and monitoring fluorescence emission by confocal microscopy. GFP fluorescence was clearly detected inside the cell, close to cell membrane at 24 h post-transfection (Figure 1g–i) and more internally at 48 h (Figure S2d–f) with a transfection efficiency of 66% ±5. Conversely, no fluorescence was detected in the control cells transfected with lipofectamine only (Figure 1d–f; Figure S2a–c). We then proceeded to the editing experiment with a Cas9 protein harboring no fluorescent tag, adapting the protocol by Liu et al. (2020) and following the same conditions of the GFP assay. 1×10^6 embryogenic calli-derived protoplasts were transfected with 1 µg of Cas9, 240 ng of sgRNA *PDS* (rather than 90 µg and 30 µg, respectively, used with the PEG protocol) and 10 µl of lipofectamine, then cultured as described for the PEG experiment (Figure 1j–l). Protoplast microcolonies developed in 10 days (Figure 1m,n) and micro-embryogenic structures in 30 days (Figure 1o–q), definitely ahead of the appearance of the same structures in PEG-treated cultures (50 days), confirming how this compound compromised the cell viability. At 50 days from lipofectamine-mediated transfection, mature embryos formed (Figure 1r,s) and

were transferred on germination media. Plants started to regenerate after 2 months (Figure 1t), and the number of Nebbiolo plants regenerated after 5 months from transfection was close to that obtained from protoplast regeneration of wild-type Nebbiolo (62 and 65 plants, respectively). These data suggested that lipofectamines had no impact on protoplast viability and embryogenic capability. Potentially edited plants were then screened by High-Resolution Melting Analysis (HRM) (Figure 1v,w), Sanger (Figure 1x), and amplicon deep sequencing (Figure 1y). Seven edited plants were obtained, of which six showed an albino phenotype (e.g. Figure 1u); four were biallelic homozygotes with small indels ranging from –2 to +1 bp, one was monoallelic with a nucleotide deletion and no albino phenotype, and two were biallelic heterozygotes (Figure 1y). The occurrence of the same type of mutation (–GT, –G, +T or –A, Figure 1x) in independent lines strengthens the possibility that DNA repair after non-homologous end-joining is not a random process but rather depends on some characteristics of the Cas9-edited region, as previously suggested (Scintilla et al., 2022). All mutations generated by the Cas9 activity led to truncated versions of the *PDS* protein (Figure 1z), and no off-target mutations were detected in the top 5 genome-wide off-target sites (off-score >0.2) predicted by the CRISPR-P 2.0 tool (<http://crispr.hzau.edu.cn/CRISPR2/>) (Figure S3).

A successful editing in woody plants, as in recalcitrant-to-regeneration wine grape genotypes, relies on a compromise among efficiency of the editing machinery delivery, cytotoxic effect, and cell viability maintenance. Compared to the PEG method, our approach greatly improved protoplast viability and led to embryo development and maturation. In addition, the regeneration of the plants was asynchronous and occurred in a period from 2 to 5 months after transfection, with regeneration times faster than what was observed in previous experiments (about 6 months) (Najafi et al., 2023; Scintilla et al., 2022; Tricoli & Debernardi, 2024). Though far from the PEG-mediated editing efficiency of the highly embryogenic table cultivars Crimson seedless and Sugraone (17.9% and 42.3%, respectively, Scintilla et al., 2022), our result (11.3%) was comparable with that obtained for the hemizygous mutation of the GFP transgene in the Thompson seedless cultivar (11%, Najafi et al., 2023) but with the important technical advantage that only one-sixtieth of editing reagents were used. We were successful with an editing that was highly homozygous in six out of seven plants, and the next objective will be to improve the editing efficiency, for example, by considering different lipofectamine types and concentrations and a further optimization of the Cas9/gRNA ratio. Moreover, the approach of Tricoli and Debernardi (2024) – although more labor-intensive than the one here adopted – has recently led to the regeneration of edited plants from different

grapevine genotypes but exclusively when a grape feeder suspension cell was supplied to protoplasts encapsulated in calcium alginate beads. Based on this, a next step could be the use of lipofection, which totally eliminates the use of PEG, combined with protoplast co-culture with active growing cell suspension. Our method is in fact effective for a recalcitrant-to-regeneration wine grape cultivar, for which an efficient DNA-free editing approach was urgently required and could be used as starting point to further optimize the genome editing efficiency in grapevine and in other species recalcitrant to regeneration.

Recently, the European Commission has proposed loosening the rules on gene-edited plants (Stokstad, 2023), opening the possibility of field trials in Europe. We believe that the obtainment of fully edited Nebbiolo grapevines devoid of exogenous DNA sequences paves the way for speeding up the artificial mutagenesis of several international, economically important wine grape genotypes. The proposed strategy may strongly contribute to solve the current and future biotic and abiotic emergences of grapevine, supporting a more environmentally and economically sustainable viticulture, while preserving the peculiar oenological features of target genotypes. For this purpose, besides the susceptibility genes already characterized and available in grapevine, such as *MLO* (*Mildew Locus O*) and *DMR6* (*Downy Mildew Resistant 6*), which were silenced to increase tolerance against powdery and downy mildews (Giacomelli et al., 2023; Pessina et al., 2016), further traits with a broader spectrum of tolerance to pathogens are under investigation in grapevine. Among those, the microRNAs found to be effective in other species (Zhu et al., 2022) could represent promising editing targets for improving grapevine tolerance to diseases.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Embryogenic callus production and maintenance

Immature flower clusters of Nebbiolo, Brachetto, Chardonnay, and Barbera (*Vitis vinifera* L.) were collected in vineyard in May 2021, 2022, and 2023 for embryogenic calli induction as previously described (Gambino et al., 2007). Briefly, the inflorescences were surface-sterilized twice for 15 min with sodium hypochlorite (1.5% commercial chlorine) and rinsed several times with sterile distilled water. Under a laminar flow hood, stamens (anthers plus filaments) and pistils (ovaries plus styles, stigmas, and receptacles) excised from flowers under a stereomicroscope were cultured on a medium containing 4.5 μM 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid and 8.9 μM 6-Benzyladenine (Franks et al., 1998; Gambino et al., 2007). After 3 months at 26°C in the dark, the obtained embryogenic calli were cultured on a medium containing 5 μM 2,4-D and 1 μM 6-BA for the maintenance of the embryogenic competence, kept at 26°C in the dark and transferred monthly on fresh medium.

Protoplast isolation

One gram of embryogenic calli of Nebbiolo was transferred in a sterile tube with 40 ml of washing buffer (WB: $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ 5 mM, NaAC

anhydrous 12 mM, mannitol 425 mM, pH 5.8, filter-sterilized with rapid flow filter units, stored at 4°C and used at RT). The calli were mixed by inversion and incubated at RT from 30 to 45 min. For the cell wall digestion, the supernatant was then discarded, and 10 ml of enzyme solution (mannitol 500 mM, NaAC anhydrous 12.5 mM, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ 5 mM, macerozyme R-10 0.6%, cellulase RS 1%, cellulysin 1.2%, pectinase 0.05% and pectolyase Y-23 0.05% pH 5.8, filter-sterilized with 0.2 μm filters) was added to the pellet. The cell suspension was mixed gently, transferred into a sterile petri dish, and incubated by shaking (30 rpm) for 2 h and 30 min at 30°C in dark conditions. The digestion progress was checked by inspecting cell aliquots at the optical microscope (Leica Microsystems DM750, Wetzlar, Germany). After digestion, the protoplasts were filtered through a 100 μm cell strainer first and 70 μm later for eliminating debris, and 30 ml of WB was added. The protoplasts were harvested by centrifugation at 100 g for 5 min at 4°C, the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in 30 mL of WB followed by a second centrifugation at 100 g for 5 min at 4°C (Sigma centrifuge 3 16PK, Osterode am Harz, Germany). For sucrose cushion purification, 20 ml of WB was added to the protoplast pellet, and the protoplast suspension was splitted into two 15 ml glass tubes. Five ml of sucrose solution (20% w/v) was slowly transferred to the bottom of the tubes and centrifuged at 100 g for 5 min at 4°C. With a glass Pasteur pipette, the interface protoplast layers of the two glass tubes were aspirated and transferred into a new tube. For the protoplast quantification, a cell-counting chamber was used, and the viability was determined by staining the protoplasts with FDA following a previously published protocol (Lei et al., 2015). Protoplast aliquots for transfection (1×10^6 cells in WB buffer) were prepared and stored at 25°C in the dark during the preparation of transfection reactions.

PEG cytotoxicity test

Embryogenic calli-derived protoplasts were quantified at the optical microscope by means of cell-counting chambers to determine the starting concentration after FDA staining. Protoplasts were then incubated with 10 μl of CRISPRMAX Cas9 Lipofectamine (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) for 90' or PEG solution varying the final concentration of PEG4000 or PEG1500 (25 or 40% w/v) and incubation times (3', 10' or 20') (PEG solution composition is reported in Table 1). The quantification at the optical microscope was then repeated, applying FDA staining. The results are the average of three quantifications for each condition.

Synthesis of single-guide RNA (sgRNA)

For sgRNA synthesis, a previously published protocol was followed with some adaptations (Wienert et al., 2018). The protospacer sequence was designed with the online tool CRISPR-P 2.0 (<http://crispr.hzau.edu.cn/CRISPR2/>) to silence the phytoene desaturase gene (*PDS*, Vitvi09g00004). The sequence was chosen according to on-target/off-target scores, location (gene exon, intron, UTR or intergenic), CG content (30–80% CG content recommended) and was added to the oligo T7Fwd (Table S1). The overlapping PCR reaction to form the sgRNA template was performed using 1 unit of High-Fidelity Taq polymerase (Phusion Plus DNA Polymerase, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), 1x Phusion Plus buffer, dNTPs 0.4 mM, oligoT7_Fwd and T7 RevLong 20 nM each, oligos T7 Amp and T7 Amp rev 2 μM each (Table S1), in a reaction volume of 100 μl . Amplification was performed as follows: initial denaturation step at 98°C for 30 sec, 35 cycles of 98°C for 10 sec, 57°C for 10 sec, 72°C for 15 sec, and final extension at 72°C for 5 min. PCR products were purified with Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega, Fitchburg, WI, USA) and in vitro – transcribed using the T7 RNA polymerase in a reaction containing: 1x Transcription buffer of T7 RNA polymerase

(Thermo Fisher Scientific), NTP mix 2 mM, DTT 5 mM, DNA 1 µg, RNase out (Thermo Fisher Scientific) 1 µl, and DEPC up to 45 µl. The reaction was incubated for 1 h at 37°C, 5 µl (100 U) of T7 RNA polymerase (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was added, and then the mix was incubated 1 h at 37°C and purified with OneStep PCR Inhibitor Removal kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, CA, USA). sgRNA was stored at -80°C.

An *in vitro* sgRNA cleavage assay was performed to check if the synthesized guide performed a proper cleavage. DNA of *Nebbiolo* extracted from leaves was amplified by PCR using primers designed to amplify about 200–500 bp surrounding the target sgRNA site (Table S1) using: 100 ng of DNA, 0.5 unit of High-Fidelity Taq polymerase (Phusion Plus DNA Polymerase, Thermo Fisher Scientific), 1× Phusion Plus buffer, dNTPs 0.2 mM, MgCl₂ 1.5 mM, and primers 0.25 µM each in a reaction volume of 20 µL. The amplification profile used was the same as reported above for the overlapping PCR reaction. 150 ng of PCR products purified with Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega) were added to spCas9 protein (Merck, Burlington, MA, USA) 250 ng, sgRNA 125 ng, 1× Buffer C (Promega), and 1× BSA in a final reaction volume of 10 µl. After an incubation at 37°C for 1 h and 65°C for 10 min, the entire reaction volume was analyzed by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel.

Protoplast transfection

Protoplast transfections were performed using polyethylene glycol (PEG)-mediated and Lipofectamine-mediated approaches. The PEG-mediated transfection was carried out following previously published protocols (Najafi et al., 2023; Scintilla et al., 2022). Lipofectamine-mediated transfection was performed following the protocol of Liu et al. (2020) with some improvements. For the preparation of RNP complex, spCas9 protein (Merck) was diluted to a 400 ng µl⁻¹ working solution using the dilution buffer and instructions provided by the manufacturer, and the *in vitro* synthesized sgRNA was diluted at 50 ng µl⁻¹ in DEPC water. For each reaction, 1 µg of spCas9 in 25 µl of WB and 240 ng of sgRNA were mixed and incubated for 10 min at 25°C. For each transfection reaction, 10 µl of Lipofectamine (CRISPRMAX Cas9 Transfection Reagent, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was diluted in 15 µl of WB, mixed and incubated for 10 min at 25°C, and then mixed with RNP complex and incubated for 15 min at 25°C. This reaction mix was merged with protoplast suspension (1 × 10⁶ cells in WB buffer), mixed with gentle fingertipping, without pipetting, and incubated at 26°C for 1 h and 30 min.

To verify the effectiveness of the Lipofectamine-mediated transfection of RNP complex in grapevine protoplasts, spCas9 protein fused with enhanced GFP (eSpCas9-GFP Protein, Merck) was used for RNP complex production with the sgRNA for *PDS*. Images of transfected protoplasts were captured using a Leica TCS SP8 laser scanning confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems) with a 20× objective lens. For Cas9-GFP detection, a 476 nm excitation wavelength was used, and fluorescence emission was detected in the 487–560 nm range. Transfection efficiency was determined by the mean values (± standard errors) of the percentage of the GFP-positive protoplasts within 10 images collected 48 h after Lipofectamine-mediated transfection with the Cas9-GFP RNP complex.

Protoplast culture and plant regeneration

Each reaction of transfected protoplasts was mixed with 10 ml of solid medium reported by Zhu et al. (1997), and three drops of 750 µl were spotted on sterile petri dishes and allowed to solidify. Ten ml of liquid medium (Zhu et al., 1997) was added to each petri dish and then incubated at 26°C in the dark by shaking at 95 rpm. After

2 weeks, the liquid medium was replaced with the same medium without glucose (Zhu et al., 1997), and after 1 month, the glucose-free medium was replaced with a germination-inducing medium (liquid GS1CA, Franks et al., 1998). The liquid GS1CA medium was refreshed monthly until embryo development. The plant regeneration from mature embryos was induced with BA following a previously published protocol (Gambino et al., 2021). Each embryo-derived plant was micropropagated independently by subculturing apical cuttings on medium without plant growth regulators and maintained at 24°C and 16/8 h day/night photoperiod.

Editing detection

Genomic DNA was extracted from each regenerated embryo-derived plant (50 mg of leaves) using the Plant/Fungi Total DNA extraction kit (Norgen Biotek, Thorold, ON, Canada), following manufacturer's instructions. The obtained DNA was used to screening the potentially edited plants through high-resolution melting analysis (HRM) (Chen et al., 2018; Dahlem et al., 2012), Sanger, and NGS amplicon sequencing.

In the HRM protocol, the sgRNA target region was amplified using primers designed to amplify about 90 bp surrounding the target site (Table S1). The amplification reaction was carried out in triplicate with a total volume of 10 µl, containing 2.5 µl of DNA, 5 µl MeltDoctor™ HRM Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and 0.2 µM of each primer. Amplification, using a CFX96 Detection System (Bio Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), was performed as follows: initial denaturation step at 95°C for 10 min, 30 cycles of 95°C for 30 sec, 60°C for 30 sec, and 72°C for 30 sec. Melting curves were generated over a 60–95°C range with an increment of 0.1°C every 5 sec. During the incremental melting step, fluorescence data were continuously acquired and analyzed using the High-Resolution Melt Software v3.0.1 (Bio-Rad).

For Sanger sequencing, PCR amplification products, obtained as above described for sgRNA cleavage assay, were purified with Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega) and cloned into the pGEM-T Easy vector (Promega) following the manufacturer's instructions. Two plasmid DNAs for each HRM-positive plant were randomly selected, isolated by Wizard Plus SV Minipreps DNA Purification Systems (Promega), and sequenced by an external service (Bio-Fab Research, Italy) using M13 forward primer. Potential off-target sequences were identified by the CRISPR-P 2.0 tool (<http://crispr.hzau.edu.cn/CRISPR2/>), and the PCR products were analyzed by Sanger sequencing using specific primers (Table S1).

For NGS amplicon sequencing, the *PDS* target site was amplified by PCR following the conditions described for sgRNA cleavage assay and using primers containing universal 5' Illumina sequencing adaptors (Table S1). The PCR products were sent to an external service (Bio-Fab Research, Italy) for library production and sequencing by the Illumina MiSeq platform (2 × 300 reads, generating 100 000 reads per sample). Alignment of FASTQ files and quantification of editing frequency were performed using CRISPResso2 with a window size of 20 nucleotides (Clement et al., 2019).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All relevant data can be found within the manuscript and its supporting materials.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Figure S1. T7E1 assay of Nebbiolo protoplasts PEG-transfected with CRISPR-Cas9 sgPDS complex.

Figure S2. Confocal images of protoplasts taken 48 h after Lipofectamine-mediated transfection with the Cas9-GFP RNP complex.

Figure S3. Sanger sequencing of predicted genomic off-target sites.

Table S1. Oligos used in the present work.

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